

THE EFFECT OF VITAMIN E SUPPLEMENTATION ON THE GROWTH OF OVARIAN FOLLICLES IN GILTS

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ABSTRACT

Eight sows were randomly assigned to two groups of four animals each and used to study the ovarian status of supplemented and non-supplemented sows in a paired t-test design. The females were slaughtered, the ovaries excised and the follicles and the *Corpus albicans* studied with the use of a 30 centimeter rule and a green tailors thread. There was no significant difference ($P>0.05$) in the number of mature follicles present on the ovaries of supplemented and non-supplemented gilts, even though numerically, there were more follicles on the vitamin E supplemented gilts.

KEYWORDS: vitamin E supplementation, ovarian follicles, gilts

INTRODUCTION

While there is little pig farmers in Nigeria can do to influence the price that they receive for their product, there are many avenues available to reduce the cost of production and increase the volume of product produced per unit of capital invested (Mullan, 1999). Assuming a gestation length of 114 days, a period of lactation of 21 days and 5 days between weaning and mating then the sow is capable of having 2.4 litters per year. Many of the sows are able to produce and wean 12 piglets per litter, making an output close to 29 piglets weaned/sow/year theoretically achievable. Close and Turnley (2004) have suggested a more realistic performance target of 24 to 25 piglets weaned/sow/year. However, in many commercial herds the average output per sow is close to 20 piglets weaned/sow/year (Smits, 2003). Achieving this is however a problem for many pig farmers because of poor reproductive performance of sows in a tropical environment. In the pig about 15-25 follicles are ovulated with an average of 16.4 (Frandsen, 1974). Litter size of pigs consists of two component traits- ovulation rate and embryonic survival, (Christenson, 1993 ;Gordon,1983), and by increasing the total production per female in the breeding herd, profitability is enhanced significantly. A technique called flushing can be used to increase the number of ova shed, particularly in animals with multiple births (sows and ewes). This involves a sudden shift in feed from suboptimal to optimal for animals that have established cyclic ovarian activity (Stabenfeldt and Edqvist, 1993). Nutritional flushing increases the potential numbers of fertilized eggs and so the number of offspring (Hunter, 1985).

Vitamin E supplementation has seen to enhance reproductive performance in gilts (Akomas, 2008; Mahan, 1991, 1994). The number of piglets and their birth weights are influenced by the vitamin E supplementation. The study therefore evaluated the effect of vitamin E supplementation on the number of Graafian follicles in gilts. This study was necessary to ascertain whether supplementation increased litter size by increasing the number of mature ovarian follicles present on the ovaries.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experimental pigs were maintained on a diet as found in Table 1 over three estrous cycles to ensure that observations were because of the treatments. Daily observations were made until pigs were observed to be on standing heat and were slaughtered on that day. The females in the experiment were grouped into supplemented and non-supplemented groups based on the optimum 15 IU obtained from previous experiments. This arrangement made the experimental design a paired t-test design. To determine the influence of vitamin E supplementation on the maturation of follicles using four females on standing heat per treatment. The control was not supplemented with vitamin E. The females were slaughtered, the ovaries excised and the follicles and the *corpus albicans* studied with the use of a 30 cm meter rule and a green tailors thread. Parameters evaluated were:

Ovarian weight - left and right,

Ovarian size – diameter (pole to pole),

Number of observable follicles measuring above 7mm.,

Number of corpus *albicans* from previous estrous cycle,

Physical counts of ovarian follicles and measurement of ovarian weight.

The diameter was measured by placing a tailors sewing thread on the observable follicles and transferring to a meter rule to take measurements in centimeters. Ovarian weight was measured using a digital scale (Mettler). After the ovaries were severed from their suspensory ligaments, they were gently placed on the mettler balance and the weights read off in grams.

Results obtained were subjected to statistical analysis to determine the difference between the supplemented and non-supplemented group means using t-test.

Table 1: Composition of experimental diets

Ingredients	T I	T II	T III	T IV
Maize offal	46	46	46	46
Wheat offal	17	17	17	17
Palm kernel cake	26	26	26	26
Fishmeal	4	4	4	4
Soyabean meal	5	5	5	5
Bonemeal	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Oyster shell meal	1	1	1	1
Vitamin(mineral premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Salt	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Vitamin E(I U)	0	7.5	15	30
TOTAL	100	100	100	100
Crude protein %	17.9	17.9	17.9	17.9

Vitamin /Mineral Premix (contents in 1000kg of mixture):

Vit. A (4,000, 000IU), Vit. D₃ (880, 000 IU), Vit. E (4,000IU), Vit K (0.8g), Vit B₁ (0.2g), Vit. B₂ (1.8g), Vit. B₆ (1.2g), Nicotinic acid (8.8g), Ca pantothenate (3.2g), Vit B₆ (.2g), Vit B₁₂ (4.8mg) choline chloride (80g), Mn (40g) Fe (20g), Zn (18g), Cu (0.8g), Iodine (0.62g), Co (0.9g), Se (0.04g)

RESULTS

The results of the ovarian studies are shown on Table 2. The results indicate that there were no significant ($P>0.05$) differences among the treatments in all the parameters measured. Neither the number of mature follicles measuring above 7mm nor the number of *corpus albicans* of the previous ovulation differed among the groups. In some cases *corpus hemorrhagicum* was seen on the ovaries. In such cases the *corpus hemorrhagicum* was counted among the matured follicles. Supplementation was also not seen to affect ovarian weights and ovarian diameter. Plates 1 – 4 are the pictorial representation of the ovaries following slaughter. Numerically there were more follicles on the supplement ovaries even though no statistical difference was observed from the groups.

Table 2: Ovarian parameters obtained following vitamin E supplementation

Parameter	Treatment groups	
	Supplemented n = 4	Non supplemented n = 4
Duration of cycle(days)	2100±0.00	21.00±0.00
Mature follicles measuring 7mm(no)		
Left ovary	9.25 ± 1.38	6.00 ± 0.71
Right ovary	8.75 ± 1.25	6.00 ± 0.75
Corpus albicans of the previous ovulation-left ovary	7.25 ± 1.11	5.75 ± 0.48
Right ovary	6.50 ± 1.19	4.50 ± 0.65
Left Ovarian weight(g)	4.46 ± 0.40	4.97± 0.03
Right Ovarian weight(g)	4.36 ± 0.31	4.67 ± 0.19
Ovarian diameter(mm)		
North pole Left ovary	1.63 ± 0.27	2.02 ± 0.27
Right ovary	1.65 ± 0.03	1.60 ± 0.24
South pole Left ovary	1.45 ± 0.21	1.60 ± 0.18
Right ovary	1.10 ± 0.17	1.30 ± 0.23
Ovarian length (cm)		
Left ovary	2.85 ± 0.25	2.68 ± 0.16
Right ovary	2.50 ± 0.22	2.55 ± 0.20
Body weight(kg)	78 ± 1.41	77.75±0.85

Plate 1: Showing ovary during standing heat in vitamin E supplement gilt Note object located in the fimbria

Plate 2: Showing ovary during standing heat in a nonsupplement gilt

Plate 3 : Showing ovary during standing heat in vitamin E supplemented gilts

Plate 4: Showing ovary during standing heat in vitamin E nonsupplemented gilts

DISCUSSION

There was no significant difference ($P>0.05$) in the number of mature Graafian follicles present on the ovaries of supplemented and non-supplemented gilts, even though numerically, there were more follicles on the vitamin E supplemented gilts. The predominant pattern of follicle development in pigs is characterized by continuous activation, slow growth to the antral stage, and rapid growth to 4 to 5mm stage followed by atresia. The only time that this pattern is broken is when a small portion of the follicle population is selected for ovulation (Guthrie, 2005). As the follicles develop, they produce estradiol, which increases steadily during the luteal stages of the oestrous cycle. Once estradiol concentrations reach a high enough level, the preovulatory surge of

FSH and LH occurs, and ovulation takes place. In this study, only mature Graafian follicles were considered. Perhaps, the picture would have been clearer if the antral follicles were studied and this is for further studies .

Pigs are multiple ovulators and one would really wonder why employ vitamin E in pig reproduction. Even though vitamin E did not influence the number of ovarian follicles significantly, it might have played a role in the well being of the oocytes. It is possible that supplementation exerted its influence not at the point of ovulation but at implantation and pregnancy. The ovulation rate is usually greater (16-17) than the uterine capacity (about 12). Because fertilization rate is high, a reduction of embryo number usually occurs by day 30 of the gestation. The mopping up ability of free radicals by vitamin E must have contributed so that the embryo loss at this time is greatly minimized. This may explain the significantly larger litter sizes observed in the vitamin E supplemented group in previous studies (Akomas, 2008). Myatt and Cui (2004) observed that in the first trimester, establishment of blood flow into the intervillous space is associated with a burst of oxidative stress. The inability to mount an effective antioxidant defense against this leads to early pregnancy loss. Oxidative stress develops when there is an imbalance between the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the scavenging capacity of antioxidants in the reproductive tract (Agarwal and Allamaneni, 2004). It has been demonstrated that vitamin E has activity against reactive nitrogen species (NOS) and peroxy radicals which are reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Brigelius-Flohé *et al*, 2002). They can interrupt free radical chain reactions by capturing the free radical, thereby imparting to them their antioxidant properties.

Further studies is recommended to trace the possible explanations of the higher litter size observed in vitamin E supplemented gilts.

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